

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE MYOCARDIUM IN ETHANOL POISONING

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Abstract

The aim is to study the pathomorphological changes in the rat myocardium after alcohol intoxication, to compare the pathomorphological changes in the myocardium during ethanol intoxication, which allows developing objective criteria for the morphological diagnosis of fatal poisoning with these substances depending on the time of their consumption.

Materials and methods. The material was obtained from 65 corpses of individuals of both sexes who died at the age of 21 to 55 years. These were the corpses of individuals who were consumers of ethyl alcohol during their lifetime. The study was carried out on the basis of practical pathological and forensic studies over the period of 2015, 2016 and 2018. The change in the microstructural and morphometric parameters of the left ventricular myocardium was assessed using light microscopy.

Results. in case of ethanol poisoning, circulatory disorders are observed in the myocardium; in case of ethanol intoxication, it is caused by changes in hemocirculation due to spastic contraction of arterial vessels, pronounced congestive venous plethora, as well as pronounced slowing down or even stopping of blood circulation in the vessels of the microcirculatory bed. A decrease in the volume fraction of cardiomyocytes with an increase in that of the interstitium and vessels, as well as destructive changes in cardiomyocytes in the form of their wave-like deformation, loss of transverse striation, foci of plasmolysis and fragmentation of muscle fibers were revealed.

Keywords: morphological changes in the myocardium, microcirculation, alcohol intoxication.

Relevance of the study. The most common cause of acute fatal poisoning in Kazakhstan is the use of ethyl alcohol, while the pathomorphology of ethanol intoxication is very diverse and its diagnosis is quite complex. This is due to the fact that alcohol intoxication causes pathology caused by damage to all organs and systems of the human body, but the main target organs - the heart and liver - are especially often affected. In the process of thanatogenesis development, depending on the organ damage, death can be caused by various types of acute organ failure - cardiovascular, pulmonary and hepatic failure, and often as a cumulative result of multiple organ failure [1,2,3,9]. In this regard, acetaldehyde plays a leading role in the development of organ pathology caused by the initial intake of ethanol. This explains the fact that death from acute ethanol intoxication can occur at any stage of its metabolism in the body. Somatic pathology of the myocardium is of great importance in ethanol intoxication, especially in chronic cases. Signs of heart failure in alcohol intoxication include such changes as destructive-dystrophic and discirculatory changes in the myocardium, lysis of myofibrils and lipid infiltration of cardiomyocytes, detected at the ultrastructural level, myocardial fibrillation and cardionecrotic effects of biogenic amines. According to Piano M.R. [10], acute alcohol intoxication usually manifests itself in a sharp swelling of acidic mucopolysaccharides and neutral mucopolysaccharides in the walls of the coronary arteries, especially the

intima, diffuse inhibition of myocardial oxidation-reduction enzymes, and at the same time there is abundant deposition of lipoproteins and neutral fat. A detailed study of the pathogenesis and pathomorphology of alcoholic cardiomyopathy was complicated by the fact that acute alcohol intoxication and long-term alcohol consumption, although they led to disruption of the synthesis of structural proteins, a decrease in the biogenesis and respiratory function of cardiomyocyte mitochondria and a decrease in the contractility of the myocardium as a whole, did not cause the formation of alcoholic cardiomyopathy in themselves.

When studying energy-dependent changes in the ultrastructure of cardiomyocyte mitochondria in cases of alcoholic heart disease, characteristic swelling of the mitochondria was recorded, especially pronounced in cardiomyocytes with uncontracted myofibrils. The authors suggest that in such cardiomyocytes the pre-process of contraction-relaxation of myofibrils is disrupted, which leads to an excess of Ca²⁺ ions in the cytoplasm, which actively accumulates in the mitochondria, causing their strong swelling [5,7]. As a result of the study conducted by A.V. Kapustin [3], pathomorphological changes in the myocardium characteristic of alcoholic cardiomyopathy were formulated. He attributed to these signs of atrophy of many cardiac muscle fibers and their combination with individual hypertrophied fibers, the absence of coronary sclerosis or its insignificant severity, small-focal cardiosclerosis of peconarogenic origin, as evidenced by

intact coronary arteries. Large-cell and lymphohistiocytic infiltrates in the epicardium and myocardial stroma are also of important diagnostic significance. According to this study, the author identified two main variants of thanatogenesis: the first from acute cardiovascular failure and the second, when death occurred from a hypoglycemic state. Among the organs that are affected by ethanol intoxication is the heart, however, at present, reliable diagnostic criteria for pathomorphological changes in the myocardium during intoxication with these substances have not been determined. Considering that the heart is one of the vital organs, the features of its pathomorphological changes in acute and chronic ethanol not only affect the variant of thanatogenesis and allow to establish the cause of death, but can also serve as a criterion to determine the time of consumption of these toxic substances, psychotropic action [4,6]. Thus, as follows from the presented data, many issues of expert assessment of pathomorphological changes of the myocardium in ethanol remain insufficiently studied. This concerns primarily the principles and approaches to the pathomorphological assessment of the myocardium, taking into account the features of the influence of acute combined intoxication against the background of existing changes in the heart muscle caused by chronic intoxication, as well as effective methods of their morphological diagnosis. Considering all of the above, **the purpose of the study** was to compare the pathomorphological changes of the myocardium in ethanol intoxication, allowing to develop objective criteria for morphological diagnosis of fatal poisoning with these substances depending on the time of their consumption.

Materials and methods of the study. The material was obtained from 65 corpses of individuals of both sexes who died at the age of 21 to 55 years. These were the corpses of individuals who were consumers of ethyl alcohol during their lifetime. The study was carried out on the basis of practical pathological and forensic medical studies over the period of 2015, 2016 and 2018. To achieve these objectives, this work was carried out, which is based on the results of qualitative and quantitative morphological analysis using a complex of both generally accepted and special methods of microscopic examination. During statistical processing, the z-criterion in the Primer of Biostatistics software package (S. Glanz, 1999) was used. The critical significance level for hypothesis testing is $p < 0.05$. Results and discussion. During the autopsy, special attention was paid to the study of the heart. After removal of the sternum and dissection of the pericardium during the section, 5 to 15 ml of light yellowish fluid were found in its cavity. In

most cases, the epicardium looked like a thin transparent plate with a smooth, shiny surface. Under the epicardium, the heart was moderately coated with fat; only in 3 cases was some turbidity and thickening noted. In 22 cases, single small point hemorrhages were detected, which were visible under the epicardium. All hemorrhages were intensely red, rounded, point-sized, from 0.1x0.1x0.1 cm to 0.3x0.3x0.3 cm. The dimensions and weight of the heart in all sectional observations were within the normative values set out in the main guidelines. The heart weight was in the range from 270 to 340 g, the quantitative indicators of the right ventricle did not exceed 4 mm, the left ventricle 13 mm. The second size of the heart, indicating dilation processes, did not exceed the long dimension of the organ. The heart was examined according to A. I. Abrikosov, modified by A. V. Smolyannikov - N. D. Nadachina. In all observations, dark liquid blood was found in the heart cavities, in some cases with red loose blood clots. The endocardium after removing blood from the heart cavities and washing its surface with water had the appearance of a shiny surface. In 4 observations, when examining the inner surface of the heart, small point hemorrhages were found, which were localized under the endocardium of the left ventricle. In all cases, the myocardium examination showed pronounced blood filling, the heart muscle had a red-brown color, slightly paler in the subendocardial sections. No macroscopic changes were noted in this group during the examination. Due to the pronounced plethora of the myocardium, no small hemorrhages could be detected during its examination. During the microscopic assessment, the condition of various layers of the myocardium was assessed: the outer subepicardial, middle intramural, and inner subendocardial. The epicardium was represented by a small, unevenly expressed layer of epicardial adipose tissue cells and adjacent subepicardial layers of the myocardium. In some fields of vision, focal subepicardial hemorrhages could be visualized in the form of focal, fine-focus clusters of erythrocytes. Most of the arteries were in a state of spastic contraction, and in addition to narrowing of their lumen, a change in the quantitative volume ratios of the lumen of the arteries and the wall was noted. When conducting light microscopy using high magnification, it was evident that the intima and muscle layer were "expanded" due to areas of thickening. Morphological assessment of the state of the arterial wall and the internal contour of the vessels made it possible to identify the appearance of a sharp tortuosity of the course of elastic fibers.

Figure 1(a,b). Pronounced plethora and paresis of venous vessels. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification 400.

Taking into account the above-described changes, the contours of these vessels took on a bizarre shape in some cases, due to which, when examining longitudinal sections, they looked serpentine and twisted, and had a stellate shape on transverse sections. When assessing the state of the endothelial cells lining the vessel, it was noted that the endothelial nuclei, due to cell deformation, were located in the form of a palisade and were hyperchromatic.

A microscopic assessment of the venous bed vessels revealed that the vessel contours were unevenly expanded due to overflow with formed elements, the silhouettes of erythrocytes were poorly distinguishable (Fig. 1, 2).

When examining the vessels of the microcirculatory bed, light microscopy and micropreparations with longitudinal sections were informative. Microvessels in longitudinal sections had a slightly enlarged lumen, due to which the usually barely noticeable with light microscopy, enlarged in volume vessels of the microcirculatory bed were quite easily visualized in the form of numerous slightly tortuous "chains" with a lumen filled with erythrocytes. Formed elements located in the lumen of the vessels formed aggregates in the form of "trains" in those places where they were tightly adjacent to each other.

Figure 2 (a, b). Focal fine-focus hemorrhage of the myocardial stroma. Stromal edema. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification 400

During the overview microscopic assessment, in all observations, the presence of a large number of focal small-focus hemorrhages in the circumference of the vessels and in the myocardial stroma was noted. Visible paravasal and stromal hemorrhages were represented by erythrocytes with clear contours and eosinophilic

staining (Fig. 2). Preferential localization of such hemorrhages in the circumference of venous or arterial vessels was not revealed in this group of observations. When examining heart preparations from the area of focal fine-focus hemorrhages, no uneven contraction of

cardiomyocytes located along the edge of the hemorrhage was observed, such as hyperrelaxation in combination with overcontracted muscle fibers, as described in blunt cardiac trauma. No changes associated with dystrophic or inflammatory processes were observed in any muscle fibers bordering the hemorrhage areas.

In almost all observations, microscopy revealed fragmentation of muscle fiber groups in left ventricular sections. As a rule, fragmented muscle fiber groups did not exceed 4-5 fields of vision. The gaps between fragments were narrow, the ends of the fragments were even, and the contours sometimes had the appearance of a jagged line.

Morphological features of fragmented muscle fibers in polarized light, with phase contrast and photochemical fluorochroming, allow us to state that the division of muscle fiber most often occurred at the locations of intercalated disks, and in the presence of contracture damage to muscle fibers, often directly at the site of contracture. In cases of general microscopy, with hematoxylin and eosin staining at low magnification, some variegation of the myocardium was noted. At high magnification parameters, it was found that this was due to uneven staining of individual muscle fibers or their individual groups, which looked more oxyphilic, while others weakly perceived eosin. Sometimes uneven staining was not observed in the entire muscle cell. Segments of muscle fibers with sharp eosinophilia looked swollen, homogenized, and the transverse striation in them was weakly defined or not defined at all.

Longitudinal striation is not clearly expressed. When examining myocardial preparations stained according to Weigert, clearly expressed fragmentation of cardiomyocytes was observed (Fig. 3a).

In all observations, a large number of subsegmental contractures (contraction bands) were observed in the preparations of the ventricles and interventricular septum. In this case, cardiomyocytes were noted with one or two overcontracted areas occupying 2-3 sarcomeres. In some preparations, several such contraction bands were distinguished in one muscle fiber.

Most often, they were located along the periphery of cardiomyocytes, not far from the intercalated disks, and were less common at a distance from them. Along the edges of these contraction bands, a section without the usual alternation of isotropic and anisotropic disks was visible.

The detected subsegmental contractures revealed during the study of the ventricular myocardium were heterogeneous; in some fields of vision, contractures were multiple, while in other fields, single lesions of muscle fibers of a subsegmental nature could be detected. In some cases, contracture subsegmental lesions were more widespread and exceeded in width the subsegmental contractures found in other fields of vision.

No differences in the prevalence and nature of subsegmental lesions of muscle fibers in the myocardial zones adjacent to focal small-focus hemorrhages or outside their zones were noted.

Figure 3(a,b). Spasm of the intramural artery, isolated extravascular erythrocytes, perivascular cardiosclerosis. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification 400.

In addition to subsegmental contractures in polarized light, in the observations of this group, bands of cardiomyocyte dissociation were found in polarized light. In these muscle fibers, the intercalated disc was a wide dark band, and the adjacent anisotropic discs had the appearance of a bright light strip. In phase contrast and photochemical fluorochroming, the expanded intercalated disc and the adjacent anisotropic discs were visible as a wide dark band and an area with reduced luminescence intensity. Microscopic examination of

the myocardium, in addition to acute changes in cardiomyocytes, moderate hypertrophy of muscle fibers of varying severity with an increase in fiber diameter and large oval-shaped nuclei was noted in 5 cases. More pronounced and widespread hypertrophic changes in cardiomyocytes were noted when examining the myocardial material of the left ventricle and the medial and lateral papillary muscles. In the subepicardial and subendocardial layers of the myocardium, altered bundles of cardiac muscle fibers were encountered, which had

a tortuous, wavy or saw-toothed appearance. A sharp bend in one or more cardiomyocytes made the muscle fibers sharply deformed. These changes are assessed as nonspecific, associated with acute damage to muscle fibers in the process of developing acute cardiovascular failure in the final stage of thanatogenesis. The systemic nature of the pathology caused by ethanol intoxication has allowed many authors to single out the term "alcohol disease" as an independent nosological entity. In this case, ethanol metabolites play a significant role in both pathogenesis and thanatogenesis, since the toxicity of ethanol itself, assessed using various criteria, is more than 10 times lower than the toxicity of its direct metabolite acetaldehyde. This confirms the existing opinion that death from acute ethyl alcohol poisoning most often occurs during its elimination, which is due to the fact that during the elimination period, the concentration of acetaldehyde reaches its maximum values [4,8,11]. Thus, as follows from the above material, in acute ethanol poisoning, pathomorphological changes are observed in the myocardium due to reactive restructuring, in response to toxic effects, of vessels of all types and calibers: arteries, veins and microvessels. The occurrence of acute circulatory disorders during ethanol intoxication is caused by changes in hemocirculation due to spastic contraction of arterial vessels, pronounced congestive venous plethora, as well as pronounced slowing down or even stopping of blood circulation in the vessels of the microcirculatory bed. All developing disorders of hemocirculation in the cardiac vascular system are combined with changes in rheological properties in the form of aggregation and sludge formation of formed elements. The toxic effect of ethanol leads to the formation of multiple focal small-focus hemorrhages in the stroma of the organ and paravascularly. Acute circulatory disorders are accompanied by increased permeability of the vascular wall. Pathomorphological changes in the myocardium, in response to developing acute intoxication, are represented by the reaction of the myofibrillar apparatus of cardiomyocytes. Disorders of blood circulation and microcirculation of the myocardium with the toxic effect of ethanol lead to the formation of acute dystrophic damage to cardiomyocytes in the form of contractures of varying severity, from subsegmental to contractures of the 1st and 2nd degree. All the above-described changes develop against the background of edema of the myocardial stroma.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Pathomorphological features in acute ethanol poisoning are represented by acute circulatory disorders, widespread multiple focal paravascular and stromal

hemorrhages, acute focal reversible damage to the myocardium of varying severity, mainly in the form of contractures - subsegmental and 1-2 degrees.

2. Morphological assessment of myocardial changes in fatal ethanol poisoning allows us to clarify the variant of thanatogenesis, as well as resolve the issue of the duration of ethyl alcohol intoxication in a specific consumer.

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